

**THE GROUNDS FOR RECOGNIZING AND IMPLEMENTING THE
DECISIONS OF FOREIGN STATE COURTS AS WELL AS FOR REFUSING
THE RECOGNITION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF DECISIONS IN THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

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The procedure for recognition and enforcement of foreign court decisions stipulated in international treaties is reflected in Chapter 33 (Articles 248-258) of the Economic Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.¹

Article 248 of the Economic Procedural Code states that the decisions on economic disputes and other cases made by the courts of foreign countries shall be recognized and enforced by the economic courts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, if the relevant international treaties and legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan provide for such recognition and enforcement. Only a court document that has entered into legal force as a result of consideration of the case can be recognized and enforced.

The procedure for recognition and enforcement of judgments of foreign courts is established in the international treaties that the Republic of Uzbekistan is a party to - the Kiev Treaty, the Minsk Convention, and the Kishinev Convention, as well as in bilateral treaties on legal assistance.

Within the framework of regional documents, the Kiev Treaty has

¹ <https://lex.uz/acts/3523891>

consolidated the mutual recognition and enforcement of legally binding decisions of competent courts among the participating states of the CIS. The Treaty requires the competence of the courts, and the procedure for recognition and enforcement consists of the list of documents to be attached to the application for recognition and enforcement, as well as the grounds for refusing recognition and enforcement. The "competent court" referred to in Article 4 of the Kiev Treaty means the court of the contracting party that has the right to consider disputes in accordance with the rules of the Treaty, whose decision is to be enforced on the territory of another contracting party. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the economic courts are considered to be such courts.²

Specifically, if the applicant has submitted all the documents required by the international treaties, in particular the Kiev Agreement, the Minsk and Kishinev Conventions, as well as Articles 250-251 of the Economic Procedural Code considering the above mentioned documents, the court will issue a ruling to recognize and enforce the decision of a foreign court. If the party whose interests are in contrast with the decision of the foreign court proves the existence of the grounds for refusal to recognize and enforce the court decision in accordance with the above-mentioned international treaties and Article 255 of the Economic Procedural Code, or if the court establishes the existence of these grounds, the court will refuse to recognize and enforce the decision of the foreign court.

One of the grounds for refusing to fully or partially recognize and enforce the final decision of a foreign court is the situation when the decision has not entered into legal force in accordance with the law of the state where the final decision was made, except for cases where the final decision must be enforced before it enters into legal force. For the recognition and enforcement of a foreign court decision, first of all, it must enter into legal force in the state where it was

² <https://lex.uz/docs/2654669>

made. Only then will the court decisions have legal force in the state where they are recognized.

Failure to notify the party to the dispute in a timely and appropriate manner about the time and place of consideration of the case or any other reason preventing the party from explaining himself to the court is a serious procedural violation of the law and is the basis for refusal to satisfy the application.

This condition is also enshrined in international treaties and serves to ensure the principle of equality of the parties before the court and the law. For example: LLC "A" (Russian Federation) filed an application to the Samarkand Regional Court, requesting recognition and enforcement of the decision of the Arbitration Court of the Tomsk Region of the Russian Federation in case No. A67-11396/2021 dated July 5, 2022, to charge 20,833.32 dollars in favor of LLC "A" from LLC "B" (Uzbekistan). During the court session, the representative of the defendant stated that he was unable to participate in the court session of the Arbitration Court of the Tomsk Region on July 5, 2022, as he was not notified of the time and place of the court session. The plaintiff's application did not contain a document confirming that the defendant was notified of the time and place of the court session in the prescribed manner. In accordance with Article 255, Part 1, Paragraph 2 of the Economic Procedural Code, if the party against whom the decision was made was not timely and properly notified of the time and place of the consideration of the case, or was unable to submit its explanations to the court for other reasons, the Economic Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan will refuse to fully or partially recognize and enforce the decision of the foreign court. Accordingly, the Judicial Board for Economic Cases of the Samarkand Regional Court, by its ruling dated September 8, 2023, refused to recognize and enforce the decision made by the Arbitration Court of the Tomsk Region of the Russian Federation in case No. A67-11396/2021 dated July 5, 2022.

The issue of the absolute jurisdiction of the court of the Republic of

Uzbekistan over the case in accordance with the international treaty or legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan is also one of the grounds for dismissing the application. Matters within the absolute jurisdiction of the courts of the Republic of Uzbekistan are specifically determined in international treaties or national legislation (Article 240 of the Economic Procedural Code).

The existence of a final and binding decision of the court of the Republic of Uzbekistan between the same parties, on the same subject matter, and the same grounds does not allow for the satisfaction of the above-mentioned application. The decision of a foreign court on a case already considered and decided by the court is not recognized as valid and is not enforced.

Even if a case between the same parties, on the same subject matter, and on the same grounds has been initiated in a court of the Republic of Uzbekistan before the initiation of proceedings in a foreign court, the application shall be dismissed.

Another reason for rejecting the application is the expiration of the deadline for enforcing the decision of a foreign court. According to Article 248 of the Economic Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the recognition and enforcement of a decision of a foreign state court must be carried out within the time limits established in international treaties. If these time limits are not specified in the international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the court decision must be submitted for recognition and enforcement within three years from the date it entered into legal force. Missing this deadline is a basis for rejecting the application for recognition and enforcement.

International legal documents enshrine the principle that a dispute must be resolved by a competent court. However, the concept of competence is not defined. Nevertheless, the competence must be provided and determined by national legislation. A decision taken by an authority that has been legally authorized to consider a dispute in a particular state can be recognized and

enforced in a foreign state. For example, the limited liability company "A" (Kazakhstan) applied to the Tashkent Regional Court, requesting the recognition and enforcement of the decision of the Specialized Interdistrict Economic Court of the Jambyl Region of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated April 1, 2022 on the recovery of \$32,550 in favor of the limited liability company "A". According to clause 9.3 of the contract concluded between the parties on January 4, 2019, any disagreements and disputes arising under the contract are considered by the court at the location of the defendant. According to Article 255, part 1, paragraph 7 of the Economic Procedural Code, if the party provides evidence that the dispute was resolved by an incompetent foreign court, the economic court of the Republic of Uzbekistan will refuse to fully or partially recognize and enforce the decision of the foreign court. Accordingly, the judicial panel for economic cases of the Tashkent Regional Court, by its decision dated September 21, 2022, rejected the recognition and enforcement of the decision of the Specialized Interdistrict Economic Court of the Jambyl Region of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated April 1, 2022 in case No. 3115-22-00-2/173.

A decision made by a competent authority of a foreign state can be overturned by that authority. A foreign court decision that has lost its force is not recognized and not enforced on the territory of Uzbekistan.

International legal documents regulating relations between the participating states govern the recognition and enforcement of foreign court judgments. Therefore, an application for recognition and enforcement must be unconditionally accepted between the cooperating states. The application for recognition and enforcement of judgments of the courts of a state that does not have an agreement will not be satisfied.

The principle enshrined in international legal documents and adopted by the majority of sovereign states that the court decision should not contradict the state sovereignty and security is of crucial importance. Since the court decision to be

recognized is executed on the basis of the national legislation of the state where recognition is sought, first of all it must not pose a threat to the state's security and sovereignty, and must not contradict its national legislation. Otherwise, the application for recognition and enforcement will be denied. For example, "A" LLC (Russian Federation) applied to the Andijan Regional Court with a request to recognize and enforce the judgment of the Voronezh Regional Arbitration Court in case No. A14-6488/2016 dated May 24, 2022, which ordered "B" LLC (Uzbekistan) to pay 417,499,400 Russian rubles in favor of "A" LLC. At the court session, the representative of the debtor requested to deny the recognition and enforcement of the judgment of the Voronezh Regional Arbitration Court of May 24, 2022, as it contradicts the public order of the Republic of Uzbekistan. After hearing the arguments and objections of the parties' representatives and examining the documents in the case, the court found that the economic courts of the Republic of Uzbekistan had made decisions on the dispute, while the Voronezh Regional Arbitration Court had issued the judgment without legal assessment of the valid decisions of the economic courts, which contradicts the principles of legality and the binding nature of court decisions established in the Economic Procedural Code, as well as the rules on inviolability of private property and prevention of unjust enrichment established in the Civil Code. According to Article 255, part 1, clause 10 of the Economic Procedural Code, if the enforcement of a foreign court judgment harms the sovereignty or security of the Republic of Uzbekistan or contradicts the fundamental principles of its legislation, the economic court of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall refuse to fully or partially recognize and enforce the foreign court judgment. Accordingly, the judicial board for economic cases of the Andijan Regional Court, by its decision dated September 26, 2023, refused to recognize and enforce the judgment of the Voronezh Regional Arbitration Court in case No. A14-6488/2016 dated May 24, 2022.

The grounds provided above may not be exhaustive, and the refusal to recognize and enforce a foreign court judgment may also be based on other grounds provided for in the international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The grounds for full or partial refusal to recognize and enforce a foreign court judgment set forth in Article 255 of the Economic Procedural Code are incorporated into the national legislation of the CIS member states and are almost identical to the conditions established in the Kiev Agreement, Minsk and Kishinev Conventions.

While these grounds are also enshrined in the Arbitration Procedural Code of Russia³, the Economic Procedural Code of Belarus⁴, and the Economic Procedural Code of Tajikistan⁵, evidence has been provided confirming that the dispute was resolved by a foreign court without authorization, and the conditions for cancellation of the decision by the competent authority of the foreign state have not been established.

The grounds cited above are in accordance with the norms of international treaties on the recognition and enforcement of decisions of foreign courts.

In most cases, the recognition and enforcement of decisions of a foreign court has been rejected on the basis of failure to properly notify the defendant (Article 255, Part 1, Paragraph 2 of the Economic Procedural Code).

In all cases of proceedings initiated for the recognition and enforcement of decisions of a foreign court, the proceedings have been terminated on the basis of the liquidation of the defendant (Article 110, Paragraph 4 of the Economic Procedural Code).

In conclusion, it is necessary to conduct a more comprehensive and detailed review and generalization of cases considered in economic courts regarding the

³ https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_37800/

⁴ <https://pravo.by/document/?guid=3871&p0=HK9800219>

⁵ https://online.zakon.kz/Document/?doc_id=30587949

recognition and enforcement of decisions of foreign courts, especially to study in detail the cases that have been reviewed and overturned (modified) in higher instances, and to provide clear explanations and instructions on the applicable procedural law norms.

Additionally, the phrase 'if the party against whom the decision was made was not timely and properly notified of the time and place of the case hearing or for other reasons was unable to submit his explanations to the court' in Article 255, Part 1, Paragraph 2 of the Economic Procedural Code is somewhat ambiguous. It would be appropriate to amend this phrase to 'if the party against whom the decision was made was not timely and properly notified of the time and place of the case hearing in accordance with the procedural legislation of the state where the case was heard.' This is because the phrase 'for other reasons was unable to submit his explanations to the court' is a broad concept that also includes the inability to participate in the court hearing, even if the party was properly notified. After all, according to Article 9(g) of the Kiev Agreement, if the other party was not notified of the proceedings, the recognition and enforcement of the judgment of the Contracting Party's court may be refused.

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